

Test-retest of open-source inversion recovery myocardial T1 mapping sequence (Open-MOLLI) for fast prototyping.

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Introduction

Standardization of T1 mapping is crucial its robustness since enable cross-site comparisons [1]. However, this requires access to vendor propriety codes, kept as black-boxes for most users. It was shown that a vendor-neutral sequence methodology may reduce sequence variations [2], and Pulseq was already used to scan the same sequences in different scanners [3]. The aim of this work was to evaluate the repeatability of the recently proposed Prototype of Myocardial T1 mapping (Open-MOLLI) [4] method at 1.5 and 3.0 T in vitro and 1.5 T in vivo and to compare it with the standard MOLLI sequence.

Methods

Open-MOLLI uses inversion and triggering schemes based on the MOLLI sequence, developed in Pulseq [5] (<https://github.com/asgaspar/OpenMOLLI>). Open-MOLLI and MOLLI was measured two times within each session in Siemens Aera 1.5 T and Vida 3.0 T. In vivo acquisitions (21 healthy volunteers 39±11y) was tested in a Siemens Aera 1.5 T. For 18 volunteers both sequences were performed two times, to study its repeatability. Parameters: TR/TE=3.04/1.52 ms, bSSFP readout with flip angle of 35°, slice thickness of 8 mm, 354×327 mm² field-of-view (FOV), 256×144 matrix size. Each bSSFP readout was obtained with an acceleration factor of 2. Clinical MOLLI was obtained with TR/TE=3.2/1.6 ms. Offline reconstruction with GRAPPA and parameter estimation were performed.

Results/Discussion

In vitro repeatability at 1.5T (Fig.1) showed mean T1 difference for MOLLI of 1.7 ms (CI (95%)=[-55 59] ms) while Open-MOLLI with mean difference of 1.3 ms (CI (95%)=[-46 55] ms).

The AHA16 model for both methods is presented in Fig. 2a, where we can see that they are similar for base and middle slices. The apex slices present higher T1 values for Open-MOLLI. Repeatability Bland-Altman analysis comparing scan 1 and 2 in Fig. 2b. The Bland-Altman analysis (fig.2) show that T1 estimates were similar between Open-MOLLI and MOLLI ($T1^{MOLLI}=1004\pm33$ ms vs $T1^{Open-MOLLI}=998\pm20$ ms), with a mean difference of -6 ms (p-value=0.33) and CI (95%)=[-62 50] ms. The apex slices present higher T1 values for Open-MOLLI. Bland-Altman analysis comparing scan 1 and 2 for MOLLI showed a mean difference of -1.5 ms (p-value=0.69) and CI (95%)=[-32 29] ms, while for Open-MOLLI there is a mean difference of -1.2 ms (p-value=0.84) and CI (95%)=[-49 46] ms, with an outlier with mean T1 difference of -80 ms.

Conclusion

The sequence Open-MOLLI can be used for T1 mapping in vivo with similar results to the clinically used MOLLI method. This sequence will increase the accessibility of T1 mapping in centres that would not be able to access the vendor package that include such sequences, allowing at the same time for a base sequence from which further improvements can easily be tested.

Novelty

This work shows the repeatability of Open-MOLLI in different scanners.

Impact

Open-MOLLI facilitates the standardisation of T1 mapping in the myocardial while also allowing the development of new quantification tools.

Disclosure

I or one of my co-authors have **no financial interest** or **relationship** to disclose regarding the subject matter of this presentation.

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Figure 1

Repeatability of MOLLI and Open-MOLLI, over 14 vials for the NIST/ISMRM phantom: a. Correlation with Pearson correlation coefficient squared; and b. Bland-Altman analysis for T1 values comparing between scan repetitions.

Figure 2

Comparison of T1 values estimated with MOLLl and Open-MOLLl over 21 volunteers: a. segmental distribution of mean T1 values and mean standard deviation (SD) according to the AHA 16-segment model; b. Correlation between MOLLl and Open-MOLLl; and c. Bland-Altman analysis for T1 values obtained with Open-MOLLl compared with MOLLl. The p-values were calculated with paired two-sided Wilcoxon signed rank tests for evaluating the hypothesis that the difference between the matched T1 samples comes from a distribution whose median is zero.

